

MODERN REQUIREMENTS AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE FOR ORGANIZING AND CONDUCTING THE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF FUTURE FINE ARTS TEACHERS

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Annotation: In this article, the need to develop artistic-creative skills in students, the main goal of developing artistic-creative skills of students is to form the young generation mature in all respects, well-rounded people necessary for the development of our society. comments are made.

Key words and phrases: pedagogical-psychological, linguistic and cultural, modern outlook, social necessity, continuous education, individual qualities, economic development, educational standards, Education and training, scientific-methodical.

Introduction

In the 21st century, the development of information and communication technologies, as in all areas, requires further improvement of the quality of education based on modern requirements in the education system, especially in the teaching of visual arts. For this reason, a lot of work is being done in our country to further develop visual and applied art, to increase the effectiveness of forming aesthetic education and creativity skills of students in the educational process. Jumaladan, restoring our national heritage in the fields of visual and applied arts, conveying the rich creative heritage of Kamoliddin Behzod to our people, perpetuating the memory of famous artists and folk masters who made a great contribution to the development of the field, post-secondary education in creative direction In order to organize education, retrain and improve the skills of personnel, and further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied art and design in our country, on April 21, 2020, PQ-4688 "Measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied art" The Presidential Decision on events" was adopted. In it, a creative selection of miniature and folk art works by "Followers of Kamoliddin Behzod", works of Kamoliddin Behzod and his followers, examples of calligraphy art, an exhibition of modern miniature works, and a practical conference on the creative process. in addition to work, among the tasks directly related to the educational process:

- to ensure the high level of educational process with the wide use of modern forms and methods of teaching, effective pedagogical technologies, electronic information resources aimed at developing the knowledge and skills of talented young professional artists;
- important tasks such as systematic improvement of curricula and programs of retraining and advanced training courses taking into account the wide introduction of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the educational process [1] were defined.

Methods

The process of implementing these tasks, without a doubt, shows the need for a new approach to teaching in order to further improve the quality of teaching fine arts in our

country and to increase the efficiency of students' ability to use the knowledge they have acquired in this subject in their daily activities. brings about. For this, taking into account the requirements set by the government through legal and regulatory documents and programs for the subject of fine arts, it is necessary to organize lesson processes not only with modern pedagogical technologies, but also with the effective use of information, communication and digital technologies.

Today, fine art is a subject in the general secondary education system of Uzbekistan, according to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 No. 187 "General secondary and secondary special, vocational education It is implemented on the basis of the decision of the Ministry of Education and Culture "On Approval of State Education Standards" and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 No. ORQ-637.

Based on these legal and regulatory documents, it can be observed that new state education standards based on the competency approach have been introduced in our country today. Based on it, the main goal of teaching fine arts in general secondary education institutions is to develop visual literacy in students, to improve artistic thinking, to acquire knowledge necessary in social life by developing aesthetic and emotional sensitivity, from them it is to teach them to use in their daily life and the competences that should be formed in the students in the subject were determined.

The main tasks of teaching visual arts in general secondary educational institutions:

- teaching to analyze and apply works of fine and practical art, artistic crafts, historical examples of architecture and design art, and modern works of art in practical activities;
- to teach to see and analyze the characteristic aspects of nature and to correctly perform the stages of processing an image or sculpture in a sequence;
- guide to the correct and conscious choice of profession, taking into account the integration of sciences based on the improvement of techniques and technologies;
- consists of formation and development of basic and scientific competencies.

Based on these tasks, the following qualification requirements are set for the graduates of each stage of general secondary educational institutions in the subject of visual arts (see Table 1.2):

Table 1.2

Classification of competencies that are formed in students at the stages.

Ability to observe, analyze and express characteristic aspects of nature	
A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can observe the shape, size, structure of nature; - can create simple images and sculptures based on the characteristics of nature; - can observe the characteristic aspects of nature, can describe them in practical work; - knows and can differentiate types and genres of fine art; - can apply the rules of perspective in practical work.
A1+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -can analyze the shape, size, structure of nature; - can work on pictures and sculptures based on the characteristic aspects of nature; -can observe and analyze characteristic aspects of nature; can describe in practical work.

A2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can artistically perceive and express the characteristic aspects of nature; - can apply the basic laws of perspective in the depiction; - when depicting nature, the image can work by following the rules of composition; - can distinguish between applied and visual arts, can analyze and make a sketch; - can analyze works of visual art of Uzbekistan and the world; can describe nature and approach creatively to work.
A2+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can artistically perceive and express the characteristic aspects of nature; - can use the laws of perspective in the depiction; - can use the laws and rules of composition when describing nature; - Can distinguish, perceive and analyze works of visual art of Uzbekistan and the world; - can perform practical work based on the types and genres of fine art.
Competence to correctly follow the sequence of steps of an image or sculpture	
A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can organize the workplace properly; - can place the image correctly on the paper surface; - is able to correctly apply primary and derivative colors when processing an image; - observes, analyzes and describes the shape structure, color, size ratios, and spatial position of simple natures in practical work.
A1+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - can correctly choose the compatibility of paper, pencil and paints; - can draw a line in various forms and situations; - able to see the shape, size, structure, unique important aspects of simple nature and acquire the ability to describe it.
A2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knows, can analyze and be influenced by works of visual art of Uzbekistan and the world; - can distinguish genres, currents and directions of fine art; - can follow image processing steps; - can distinguish between the main part and small parts of nature; - can correctly apply auxiliary lines used in drawing; - separates the shadow-light parts in image processing, can use them in the work process; - can correctly apply primary and secondary colors during image processing; - can do the stages of working with plasticine or clay.
A2+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - artistically analyzes works of art of Uzbekistan and the world and can meaningfully express the nature of the work; - knows the means of expression of works of fine art and can apply them in practice; - can follow the rules of color science in applied art; - can use special materials and working tools.

- Based on the goals and objectives of the subject of visual arts in secondary schools of general education and based on the state standards of education, the formation of the above-mentioned qualifications and skills of students is carried out in the following context.

- 1. Perception of existence (in grades 1-4).
- 2. Artistic construction (in grades 1-4).
- 3. Fundamentals of art studies (in grades 5-7).
- 4. Description according to nature (in grades 1-7).
- 5. Composition activity (in grades 1-7).

- Based on the age characteristics of the students, the work carried out in these areas is formed on the basis of the principle of simple to complex skills. Repetition of the content of lessons across classes requires the creators of science textbooks to regularly and consistently describe the material, to plan the topics in depth, taking into account the age characteristics of the students of each class.

- At a time when steps are being taken towards the establishment of New Uzbekistan with the initiatives of our country's president, the attention and demand for people who have a wide range of thinking, have deep knowledge, are mature in their field and can meet the demands of the times is increasing, once again, It intersects the issue of modernized education and the introduction of quality organized education. For this reason, the formation of a person who is knowledgeable, enterprising, active in society and can conquer the world with his work is becoming a requirement of today. From the point of view of the current era, it is important for teachers to organize training sessions taking into account the following criteria in the formation of a person who can meet such requirements and embody the above-mentioned characteristics:

- - Application of modern and advanced educational technologies in lessons;
- - Establish effective use of digital technologies in the organization of training sessions;
- - Adapting the highly effective results of international experiments to the education system of our country and putting them into practice.

Results

The teaching of fine arts also has a special importance in the general secondary education system, and it has wide opportunities to positively solve the issue of raising a mentally healthy generation and to form professional skills of young people. By studying art and the world of artists, the social significance and characteristics of art, and its pictorial means of expression in fine arts classes, students learn about the beauty of the environment, visual, applied art, and architecture. learning to see, appreciate and protect is done.

Therefore, first of all, the modern education system requires the teacher of the subject of "Fine Art" to rely on the important principle of the content of this subject - "from life-through-art-to-life", that is, students' personal-life based on their experiences, it requires the organization of classes in accordance with their professional interests. When working with children, today's teacher should focus on the use of educational methods and methods that ensure the activation of mental and practical skills of students, help them to develop their creative abilities more effectively. For this purpose, the teacher should make wider use of the conditions and opportunities of the educational institution.

Also, effective development of creative ability, enthusiasm, and interest of each student, depending on the personal characteristics and possibilities:

- to give creative tasks with a clear solution;
- it can be done by methods of activating and directing students' creative abilities through practical training.

The fact that the amount of lessons allocated for Fine Arts in general education schools is 1 hour per week puts a double responsibility on the teacher to create sufficient skills in the student. Because the hours allocated to the subject and the time spent on mastering the subject are different. For example, 60-90 minutes are usually allocated for the construction phase of a still life in pencil drawing. Here, taking into account that the still life consists of 3-4 items, it will take the student 15-20 minutes to completely build 1 item. In general education schools, for the formation of building skills, in the example of the 1st grades, several topics such as "Working a flag picture", "Working a clock picture", "Working a leaf picture" are given, each of which has 45 minutes of time. In traditional classes, 5 minutes of the 45 minutes allocated for one subject are the preparation and introduction part of the lesson, 10 minutes are allocated to the explanation of the rules of implementation by the teacher, 15-20 minutes are allocated to practical implementation and 5 minutes are allocated to the final part of the lesson, and the remaining 10 minutes are used to complete the work. It will be possible to understand that mastering will cause difficulty in the student. This requires a creative approach from the teacher to create knowledge and skills about the subject, to help them understand the essence of the work, to be able to properly plan and use time effectively, to create the necessary experiences for students.

Visual art is often concerned with emotional, personal and subjective issues, and it works not only on the basis of concrete and concrete knowledge, but also on the basis of experiential knowledge. Experiences in the visual arts are important in the formation of aesthetics in the participants of the process, and the knowledge generated as a result of this aesthetic experience is always organized and creates solid knowledge.

At this point, in relation to the teaching of visual arts, rather than the teaching methods that were formed in the 20th century and are currently widely used in the educational system of Uzbekistan, they are currently used in the world experience and have their own positive impact. Mastering and using methods such as "Experiential learning" and "Project method" that have brought fruit is one of the important issues of today.

Secondly, training in the subject of "Fine Art" allows not only to practice the basics of painting, sculpture, graphics based on manual labor, to get acquainted with various types of folk arts and crafts, but also to gain knowledge about modern information technologies. It also includes knowledge of fields such as demanding design and architecture. Here, in the process of improving knowledge and skills about modern design and architecture, digital technologies, in particular information and communication technologies and graphic applications, are of great importance.

Discussion

Materials in multimedia format created with the help of digital technologies have an incomparable potential in the field of education with the ability to clearly present images, create special effects for deeper understanding of information, and provide a wide range of visual information [4].]

The teacher's literacy in these digital technologies has a special place in his organization of classes, quick and high-quality delivery of information, and the formation of modern knowledge in students. It is not important for a modern teacher to have an encyclopedic memory (this feature, unfortunately, belongs to only a small percentage of people), - today everyone has the opportunity to access all the artistic heritage of the world at any moment thanks to the Internet.

The ability to work with a computer increases the activity of both subjects of the educational process, leads to the individualization of the educational process, the development of the student's personality is encouraged - his decision-making independence, initiative, requirements for accurate performance of tasks increase, the feedback between the teacher and the student on mastering the subject increases significantly. These are important features for pedagogical activity and should be reflected in the activity of an artist-teacher.

If we pay attention to the pedagogical side of the issue, it should be noted that the introduction of computer technologies helps to implement the main principles of education - the principles of demonstrability and convenience. The possibilities of using manuals (electronic or printed) in the educational process, as well as their independent production and preparation of visual material for various pedagogical needs are implemented on the basis of digital technologies. An artist-teacher with skills and knowledge in the field of computer technologies can significantly facilitate and speed up the process of mastering a block of theoretical and practical knowledge in different age groups of students, as well as significantly improve the method of presenting the studied information. 4]

In the 21st century, the wide spread of digital technologies and their reaching all levels of the population had a very positive impact on social life, including the education system. This, in its place, pushes forward the issues of further development of pedagogical and information technologies of teaching and thereby increasing the effectiveness of teaching.

In particular, the process of teaching visual arts is no exception. Because, as the field of education is gaining great importance today, new teaching methods are emerging, especially these methods are based on the principle of "Teaching" and the principle of "Getting Education" and the main goal is to teach students about science. it is important that they can use their knowledge, skills and abilities in their life activities. The subject of visual arts is an integral and important part of the educational process in school, as it not only provides knowledge, but also forms personal characteristics and includes creative processes. Also, the development of digital technologies is used to convey the concepts of graphic education to students in visual art classes, to familiarize them with the knowledge of the history and theory of visual art, and to form skills related to the field of design, which are most likely to be used in future activities. has been providing many opportunities.

Therefore, the modern teaching process of visual arts allows teachers to enrich their experience with new - student-oriented teaching methods, to master working with digital technologies that are widely used in the world, and in the field of design is setting the tasks of equipping the classrooms at the level of modern requirements for the effective use of the used applications and the meaningful and high-quality organization of lessons.

At this point, it should be noted that despite the fact that the government of our country has developed a number of decisions and decrees to improve the effectiveness of education, including the teaching of fine arts, some aspects still need attention and reforms. .

For example, although many technical equipments are required for effective teaching of visual arts nowadays, some schools are not equipped with such technologies. As a result, there are some obstacles in the introduction of new pedagogical technologies.

Most importantly, despite the increasing modern requirements for the art room and its equipment, art classes are held in ordinary classrooms and desks in many secondary schools. Because there is no legal and regulatory document on furnishing and decorating the art room.

Digital technology was founded about 100 years ago with the use of wireless electronic communications. Telegraph messages and radio transmitters are examples of our idea. Since then, technology has advanced rapidly, resulting in radio recording, film, television, computers, CDs, and the Internet.[6] Digital technology has become a very useful tool for instant messaging and keeping people informed about local and international news. This, in turn, entered the education system, like all other areas of society, and had a great impact on its formation and development.

From the second half of the 20th century, the foundation was laid for the formation of new - Digital technologies, which eliminate transmission errors and effectively perform the same task by converting analog signals to digital signals.

Digital technology has been around for over 50 years and is widely used in computers and other electronic equipment. Since the early 1960s, teachers and computer scientists began to use computers for educational purposes. Initially, it was used only for reading and writing to provide instructions on how to use the computer, and later to solve some time-consuming problems, since the interaction between users and the computer was not high. However, with the invention of inexpensive microcomputers and the integration of text, graphics, and color, computers quickly spread to businesses, schools, and homes.[7] Ultimately, the possibilities of using digital technologies in education have expanded.

Today, digital technologies are becoming an integral part of development in many countries of the world, and their importance in improving the educational process and its effectiveness is also increasing as part of ensuring a more sustainable future.

This has been specifically highlighted in the "Education for Sustainable Development Goals" program adopted by UNESCO in 2015 as part of "Education 2030". In particular, about the educational process aimed at realizing the goals set in the program, Irina Bokova says: - "When we think about the role of education in global development, we need fundamental reforms, because it is an important education for the well-being of individuals and the future of our planet. secret shows. ... Now, more than ever, education has the responsibility to prepare for the challenges and aspirations of the 21st century, to inculcate the kinds of values and skills that lead to sustainable and inclusive growth and peaceful coexistence." [8]

Conclusion

In conclusion, if we look at the educational system and its content of the most developed countries in the field of education, we can see that digital technologies, which are one of the greatest achievements of the 21st century, are widely used. For example, in the countries of Finland, South Korea, and Denmark, which in 2020 have the most effective education system in the world, digital technologies play a major role in the education system.[9]

For example, Catherine Tracy Farley in her doctoral dissertation on "Effectiveness of Teaching in the Digital Era: Computerized Technologies, Game Technology Improvement Methods, and Interactive Learning Processes" focused not only on pedagogics, but also on the formation of skills through practical implementation. but also discussed effective ways of using digital technologies. In particular, he - "In my opinion, the integration of technology tools and improvisation methods will ensure equal education, increase efficiency and solidarity among members working in small groups, student initiative, that is, authority, leads to the creation of a teaching style based on independence and self-management.

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